

METHODS OF INDEPENDENT LEARNING ENGLISH. BEST ENGLISH LEARNING TECHNIQUE

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In addition to the system of repetition and reinforcement with which we learn the language in many educational institutions, there are also interesting and unusual methods of learning English created by teachers around the world. Strictly speaking, there are as many people as there are opportunities to learn English (and new ones appear every year), so even your usual routine can be considered a learning system. But it's not about that - we're talking about popular systems that are used by thousands or even millions of people. Choosing one and sticking to it can be difficult. And if it also turns out to be ineffective, time is wasted. Therefore, it is not worth it to choose which method to choose, and also to approach learning English mainly.

The most effective English learning methods and strategies you can find online. But it is up to the student to decide which one is more suitable for the individual student.

LEARNING ENGLISH WITH DOCTOR PIMSLER'S METHOD.

This is a very popular method of learning English, which involves regular repetition of learned material while learning new ones. The main feature of the Pimsler-style curriculum (sometimes incorrectly called the "Pilsner method") is the presence of a constant conversational speaker, with whom the student can start a conversation or simply turn. Courses using this system still include active communication with pre-recorded audio transmissions. In addition, each lesson lasts half an hour, and it is recommended not to start a new one immediately after one lesson.

Among the advantages of this learning method:

- ❖ material consistency;
- ❖ ensuring that the student fully mastered the material before moving on to the next topic;
- ❖ duration of individual lessons;
- ❖ the ability to download a playlist, name it "Dr. Pimsler's English" and listen to it while traveling on the subway or bus.
- ❖ But there are also disadvantages:

- ❖ the duration of the entire Pimsler course is 45 hours on average (90 lessons of 30 minutes each);
- ❖ at the recommended pace of listening to the course, it is very easy to forget the material between classes;
- ❖ how fast a student learns English depends not only on him, but also on the speaker, who can slow down the systematic learning process.

OXFORD AND CAMBRIDGE METHODS.

These systems for teaching English were developed by English professors (it's easy to guess: both Cambridge and Oxford are in Britain), so the level of confidence of students is quite high. Moreover, these systems have been around for more than 60 years and have managed to prove themselves to people around the world. The differences between them are minimal. In both cases, the teacher is a person who knows English perfectly, in most cases it is a native language. Teachers not only tell children the rules, but also immerse them in an oral environment, encourage independent speech and writing in English. Therefore, it is one of the best ways to learn English. The only significant difference is that the Oxford system encourages only speaking and listening. Of course, the child will learn how to write words. But first of all, he learns to use them in a conversation, logically construct sentences, and independently construct verbal expressions. The Cambridge system doesn't ignore writing that much.

METHODS OF SPECIAL SERVICES

Under this phrase lie many different systems for quickly learning foreign languages, each of which in some way originates from programs taught to scouts and spies. This phenomenon is not new, such programs have been known since the 60s. It is impossible to know for sure whether any special service used one of these teaching methods, but currently, express courses for learning English using associative methods are collectively known as "special service methods". The curriculum is different, e.g:

- ❑ separate words are built together into any sentence, henceforth they are connected with each other;
- ❑ foreign words are remembered together with relatives in sound or spelling;
- ❑ whole sentences are memorized for a few words.

Many people think that this is the best way, but it is not. It is difficult to judge how effective this method is, since the average learner memorizes most of his vocabulary by association. And such a "crash" course deprives the student of

writing and writing. Such techniques may suit service agents, but are hardly difficult for the average person.

MATRIX METHOD.

The matrix method is very simple: the student is offered expressions for various life situations, he listens, says and writes them down. The student should have complete discipline supported by the teacher. When the matrix method vocabulary, syntax, speech and the whole language hits a person. The method is difficult, it requires discipline, independent control of the process and a clearly defined schedule. Therefore, the curriculum is pre-structured and can be planned before the lesson begins, rather than during it. This is by no means a quick method, but it is very effective.

AN UNTRANSLATEABLE WAY OF READING ENGLISH.

Similar approaches to learning have appeared relatively recently in a very large environment of people who are taught the rules in school and, as a result, never speak English. And they concluded that one practice is enough. An interesting conclusion, but far from the truth.

This unusual method is just the other edge of an unsharpened sword, because now the child does not understand what he is saying in principle. Of course, if you first memorize speech patterns without any meaning (like a constructor), and then finish reading the meaning of these words, you can even achieve a very coherent speech. In this case, the child pronounces well, but he does not know what he is doing at all.

As with everything, the best is the golden mean, and it's not worth experimenting on a child with a method that doesn't have many textbooks. If the parent is discriminating in the child's lack of practice, he can sometimes speak to him in English.

BEST ENGLISH LEARNING TECHNIQUE.

The competition between teachers and English courses is driving the emergence of different teaching methods. Some of them promise extremely fast results, others are impressive with a unique approach. But in practice, best practices are ways of working, that is, methods that produce real, specific, and sustainable results. And there are not many of them. There are probably only three main things.

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